

THE ROLE OF MICROORGANISMS IN THE ECOLOGICAL CONDITION OF SOIL

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Abstract. *The article examines the influence of heavy metals, such as Cr, Ni, Cd, Pb, and Cu on humus content and mobile forms of nutrients (NPK) in various types of irrigated soils, with contamination levels 3, 5, and 10 times higher than the maximum permissible concentration (MPC). The study found that heavy metals affect soils differently depending on their type, with the greatest stress observed in the humus content of meadow-serozem soils, particularly in cases contaminated with cobalt and nickel.*

Keywords: *soil, heavy metals, microorganism strains, humus, nutrients (NPK).*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that each type of micro-macroelements present in the soil, along with ensuring soil fertility, has a positive and negative effect on the agrochemical state of the soil with an increase or decrease in the content of ions of elements in the soil environment. Thus, the soil constantly contains iodine, aluminum, lithium, vanadium, titanium, lithium, sodium, chlorine, silicon, copper, molybdenum, zinc, silver and boron as microelements, and the most essential macroelements include phosphorus, potassium, nitrogen, sulfur. For plants, such elements as iron and magnesium are distributed. Depending on the level of provision of each element in the soil, plants use them completely or partially for growth. But with their increase, humus and soil nutrients necessary for plants go into a state of stress.

Literature review. Due to the increased use of agrochemicals and inorganic fertilizers, modern agricultural practices lead to soil pollution, which leads to the degradation of ecosystems and the environment [5, 7, 17]. Heavy metals accumulate during the processing of minerals, while some of their parts remain exposed to the influence of floods and winds, move to different places despite being part of the soil, and cause serious harm to plants [1, 8, 9]. Heavy metals are responsible not only for changing the composition of the soil, but also form the basis of plant stress, leading to crop failure [1, 10, 16]. Heavy metal pollution in modern agriculture has become a serious problem in a number of developing and underdeveloped countries due to various socio-economic, scientific and developmental problems [3, 9, 11].

Definitely, these strategies open a new perspective in biotechnology by enabling the development of a complex biological system to produce a better microbial system capable of combating heavy metal pollution [2, 6, 12]. Heavy metals affect soil microbiology and alter the rhizosphere relationships between plants and microorganisms, affecting soil properties, plant growth, plant type, agricultural land productivity, etc. [15, 4]. Due to their high surface area to volume ratio, which is directly related to their high reactivity, nanotechnology-based materials

have also been explored for micro remediation of heavy metals [9, 13, 14]. In this study, soil pollution with heavy metals, their dramatic impact on agrochemical processes, as well as the reduction of metal ions due to the introduction of microorganism strains or their transformation into a less effective type of ions, identify groups of microorganisms that lead to the restoration of the agrochemical state of the soil, and through them, the microbiological dependence on the creation of biopreparations.

Object of the study. Agrochemical state of the soil composition, the state of humus supply can compete with soil pollution. The effect of toxic heavy metals on mobile forms of microbiological preparations in typical gray soils of Dekhkonabad and Guzor districts of Kashkadarya region and typical gray soils of Pastdargom district of Samarkand region is considered. Laboratory experiments on the restoration of heavy metal ions were carried out using biopreparations and strains isolated from microorganisms in various contaminated soil environments. Research methods. In a laboratory experiment, 3 kg of soil were placed in plastic containers with a capacity of 5 liters, a diameter of 20 cm and a height of 25 cm. The soil was artificially polluted by separating salts of heavy metals (Cr, Ni, Pb, Cd, Cu) into 3, 5 and 10 times the permissible amount (REM) for the soil. All variants, except the control, were carried out in 2 replicates, 20 variants, 39 variants in the soil of each region, a total of 117 experiments in pots were carried out. The object of the study is typical sierozems of Pasdargam and Dehkanabad regions and meadow sierozems of Guzor region (Table 1).

Table 1

Experimental scheme on soils of selected territories of Dehkanabad, Pastdargom and Guzor districts

N.	Variants	Addition of 3 kg of heavy metal salts in excess of REE to soil composition		
1	Control soil	-	-	-
2	Control soil + microorganism strains (background)	-	-	-
3	Background + Cr REM	3 times	5 times	10 times
4	Background + Ni REM	3 times	5 times	10 times
5	Background + Cd REM	3 times	5 times	10 times
6	Background +Cd REM	3 times	5 times	10 times
7	Background + Pb REE	3 times	5 times	10 times
8	Background +Co REM	3 times	5 times	10 times

In the second laboratory experiment, 20 grams of soil samples were contaminated with three different amounts of toxic (Zn, Co, Pb, Cu, Cr) salts in 3, 5 and 10 times greater than REE, and the experiments were carried out on 70 Petri dishes with strains of microorganisms. Soils contaminated with toxicants were inoculated with the strains of microorganisms presented in Table 2 below, and their effect on soil humus and nutrients, as well as the amount of toxicants, was observed.

Results obtained. It is known from many literary sources that as a result of the entry of toxic elements into the soil, the humus content of the soil changes in different ways, in many cases humus is subject to stress. In our experiments, 2 and 4 months after artificial soil contamination, 3 kg of soil in containers were checked for humus and the following results were obtained. The

content in the control soil of irrigated typical sierozems of Kalii Zavod park, located in Dehghanabat district, is 1.144% with humus, while it is noted that the strains of microorganisms in the control variant are 0.181% more than the humus of the control variant. It is evident that counter-inoculation of microorganism strains for the copper element has little effect on the humus content. The amount of humus was 0.065 and 0.035% higher than the control in the variants with 5- and 10-fold contamination of the REE composition of the soil with copper ions. An increase of 0.041% was found in 4 variants contaminated with nickel ions 3 times higher than REE (Table 3).

Table 2

Strains of microorganisms used in the experiment

1	<i>Acinobacter lwoffii</i> (№1)	7	<i>Enterobacter ludwigii</i> (№11)
2	<i>Bacillus pumilis</i> (№3)	8	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (№13)
3	<i>Bacillus atropheus</i> (№4)	9	<i>Bacillus cereus</i> (№14)
4	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i> (№5)	10	<i>Bacillus pumilis</i> (№24)
5	<i>Bacillus atropheus</i> (№7)	11	<i>Lactobacillus sakei</i> (№28)
6	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> (№10)		

Table 3

Positive effect of humus content on stress and microorganism strains, %

№	Variants	irrigated typical sierozem of Dehghanabad district		irrigated typical sierozem of Pastdargom district		irrigated meadow sierozem of Guzor district	
		Time of sampling of experimental soil samples					
		March	May	March	May	March	May
1	Soil Control	1,144±0,008	1,205±0,015	1,100±0,024	1,204±0,018	1,144±0,024	1,171±0,018
2	Soil control + microorganism strains (Background)	1,325±0,023	1,420±0,001	1,330±0,002	1,218±0,003	1,270±0,005	1,280±0,011
3	Background+Cr oREM (3*)	0,738±0,003	1,593±0,038	0,692±0,004	0,980±0,002	1,034±0,003	0,880±0,017
4	Background +Ni REM (3*)	0,848±0,002	1,746±0,001	0,763±0,007	1,008±0,002	0,826±0,001	1,177±0,003
5	Background +Cd REM (3*)	0,629±0,001	1,319±0,013	0,826±0,002	0,896±0,007	0,748±0,001	0,880±0,017
6	Background +Cu REM (3*)	0,655±0,002	1,538±0,004	0,847±0,003	0,924±0,007	1,067±0,006	0,990±0,016
7	Background +Pb REM (3*)	0,936±0,001	1,427±0,001	0,774±0,006	0,882±0,006	1,119±0,008	1,106±0,024
8	Background +Co REM (3*)	0,728±0,001	1,289±0,001	0,868±0,001	0,910±0,009	0,957±0,006	0,815±0,004
9	Background +Cr REM (5*)	0,923±0,004	1,372±0,004	0,813±0,004	1,092±0,006	1,130±0,006	1,199±0,007
10	Background +Ni REM (5*)	0,759±0,002	1,594±0,001	0,616±0,004	1,092±0,006	0,695±0,007	1,067±0,005

11	Background +Cd REM (5*)	0,659±0,002	1,538±0,001	0,693±0,002	1,074±0,001	0,681±0,004	1,199±0,001
12	Background +Cu REM (5*)	1,209±0,002	1,329±0,001	1,166±0,001	1,120±0,001	1,163±0,007	1,090±0,014
13	Background +Pb REM (5*)	1,012±0,001	1,123±0,008	0,703±0,002	1,134±0,001	1,196±0,001	1,199±0,001
14	Background +Co REM (5*)	0,751±0,034	0,889±0,008	0,840±0,011	1,064±0,005	0,341±0,006	1,133±0,002
15	Background +Cr REM (10*)	0,670±0,001	1,089±0,007	0,891±0,005	1,261±0,001	0,484±0,009	0,352±0,009
16	Background +Ni REM (10*)	0,440±0,003	1,053±0,007	0,759±0,005	1,274±0,002	0,385±0,007	0,814±0,002
17	Background +Cd REM (10*)	0,705±0,005	1,077±0,007	0,825±0,001	1,540±0,002	0,517±0,004	0,825±0,008
18	Background +Cu REM (10*)	1,179±0,001	0,968±0,008	0,649±0,007	1,388±0,004	0,561±0,001	0,748±0,003
19	Background +Pb REM (10*)	1,057±0,005	0,813±0,001	1,001±0,001	1,456±0,001	0,616±0,002	0,495±0,008
20	Background H+Co REM (10*)	0,683±0,003	1,077±0,005	0,660±0,001	1,484±0,002	0,401±0,010	0,715±0,019

Moreover, even in irrigated typical sierozems of Pastdargom district, contaminated with copper 5 times, the stress state of humus in comparison with the control was absent and was established to be 0.066% higher than in the control. In the analyses carried out in May, the least stress state of copper was observed in 12 variants contaminated with copper 5 times. An excess of 0.184% was found in 18 variants contaminated with copper element 10 times in comparison with the control variant. In addition, it is possible to compare the release of humus from the stress state with the metal sorption of microorganism strains in soils contaminated with salts of heavy metals Cr, Ni, Cd, Cu, Pb and Co 10 times higher than REE (Table 3).

With 10-fold contamination of gray meadow soils of Guzor district with individual heavy metals, it was found that the level of influence on the humus content was high in the following series: Co → Ni → Cr → Cd → Cu (Table 3). The potassium content in the soil taken from the vegetable garden of the potash plant in Dehkhatabat district is high (Table 4). Mobile forms of potassium were observed in the irrigated soils of Pastdargom district, and in the soil of the control variant - 249 mg / kg (200-300 mg / kg is the average supply). In the control soils, 788 mg / kg were found, and in the variants using microorganism strains - 919 mg / kg of mobile potassium. As with the influence of heavy metals on the state of humus, a decrease in potassium was observed in the variants contaminated 3, 5, 10 times with copper REE compared to the control. A decrease of 254 mg/kg was observed in the contaminated variant 10 times compared to the control (Table 4).

In the next series, it was found that the effect of lead and cobalt on the mobile form of potassium was strong, and in gray soils the content of Pb ions decreased to 621→384 mg/kg in variants contaminated by 5 and 10 times, while in variants contaminated with cobalt it decreased to 461→402 mg/kg or decreased under stress conditions. These conditions caused a decrease in the amount of potassium found in typical gray soils (Table 4).

Besides that, mobile forms of phosphorus are high (>60 mg/kg) in the group of irrigated soils brought from Pastdargom district, in the control - 62 mg/kg, in the control - 53 mg/kg (45-60 mg/kg). Soils of Dehkhonabad and Guzor districts - 47 mg/kg in gray meadow soils (Table 4). In the soils of the control variant 3-5-6, variants with Cr, Cd, Cu ions, 3 times more polluted than REE, in all variants with 5-fold pollution caused a decrease in the phosphorus content in typical irrigated gray soils, and in the soils of Pasdargom and Guzor districts with low humus content, 10-fold pollution with heavy metals in the variants, a sharp decrease in the phosphorus content was observed (Table 4).

Table 4

The influence of microorganism strains on the state of toxicants on the content of mobile nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium in the soil

Variants	Dekhkonabod	Pastdargom	Guzor	Dekhkonabod	Pastdargom	Guzor	Dekhkonabod	Pastdargom	Guzor
	K ₂ O			P ₂ O ₅			N-NO ₃		
Soil Control N/A)	788±23	249±31	335±17	53±15	62±12,3	47±2	34±2,0	31±2,1	27±4,1
N/A + Mic. strain (Background)	831±29	245±9,5	330±10	54±1,6	58±13,2	34±0,1	35±3,03	37±2,7	29±0,35
Background+ Cr (3*)	919±164	452±4,7	349±6	48±11,7	52±2,0	43±1,7	32±6,02	33±2,03	24±0,88
Background+ Ni (3*)	842±149	379±26	405±22	66±9,8	31±1,2	56±8,9	34±4,01	32±2,07	26±0,65
Background+ Cd (3*)	765±217	367±5	294±3	48±12,7	31±6,5	41±7,0	32±5,1	33±2,5	27±0,74
Background+ Cu (3*)	661±323	354±7	324±39	50±14,5	26±4,8	33±0,42	29±2,03	30±1,02	25±0,55
Background+ Pb (3*)	783±150	354±1,5	374±08	56±7,5	31±1,6	47±0,64	30±2,2,2	34±2,04	27±0,14
Background +Co (3*)	598±5,0	330±9	260±12	45±2,3	33±3,3	35±2,7	31±3,2	38±1,0	22±0,58
Background+ Cr (5*)	764±0,90	490±2	455±26	39±4,9	34±1,3	52±0,9	35±1,8	32±0,75	24±0,67
Background+ Ni (5*)	726±216	381±21	385±46	48±10,2	30±5,0	51±0,7	32±2,4	32±0,84	26±1,45
Background+ _Cd (5*)	901±6,06	378±1,4	407±26	59±2,9	36±6,5	50±0,2	31±2,5	30±0,65	23±2,11
Background+ Cu (5*)	655±169	337±7	376±47	50±14,1	32±2,3	56±0,1	30±2,4	29±0,88	27±2,45
Background+ Pb (5*)	621±74	332±5	363±21	54±21,7	30±0,1	56±0,2	34±2,1	24±0,75	25±2,33
Background+ Co (5*)	461±86	341±14	377±35	46±0,9	31±0,6	55±7,3	30±2,2	35±0,77	24±0,28
Background+ Cr (10*)	772±41	281±0,2	171±09	56±9,6	67±6,2	16±0,1	28±1,7	31±1,15	26±0,76
Background+ Ni (10*)	602±43	223±8	291±134	58±3,3	57±13,4	34±1,3	27±3,05	28±2,01	24±0,54
Background +Cd (10*)	732±98	236±3	314±140	58±6,0	48±11,2	39±25,7	25±1,8	27±1,45	21±0,36
Background+ Cu (10*)	577±253	240±10	344±239	58±7,5	60±6,8	43±12,7	28±2,01	26±1,75	23±0,86
Background+ Pb (10*)	384±79	229±37	175±4,2	49±6,9	56±3,1	29±10,0	27±3,01	24±2,05	22±0,97
Background+ Co (10*)	402±106	199±11	230±27	49±17,0	38±1,1	23±0,3	26±1,9	21±0,95	19±2,08

Explanation: Pollution with heavy metal salts is 3-5-10 () times greater than REE*

In versions 10 times more contaminated with lead and cobalt. In gray meadow soils, a decrease of 29 and 23 mg/kg was observed. With a decrease to 18-24 mg/kg, it turns out to be deficient, that is, it belongs to the group of 15-30 mg/kg. The highest amount was observed in the version with 10-fold contamination with chromium under stress conditions with a decrease of 31 mg/kg compared to the control (Table 4).

In further observations, it is possible to determine the regeneration of phosphorus by sorption of ions by strains of microorganisms. Nitrogen in mobile form in the control variants of experimental soils was provided moderately (30-50 mg/kg) and low (20-30 mg/kg), while it was believed that the influence of toxicants also causes the nutrient element N. -NO₃ to enter a state of stress. Nitrogen in the control soils of the potash garden of Dehkhanaabad district and meadow sierozems of Guzor district was 34 mg/kg. It was found to be 27 mg/kg. Microorganism strains were introduced in control variants into the soil brought from Pastdargom district. An increase from 31 mg/kg to 37 mg/kg was observed.

Nitrogen stress state in a toxic environment from REE heavy metals. It was found that in contaminated variants it is 10 times higher. The highest state was observed for the cobalt ion. A decrease was observed in irrigated typical sierozems at doses of 8 and 10 mg/kg and in meadow sierozems at doses of 8 mg/kg. The state of nutrient recovery is restored after bioaccumulation or purification of plants from toxicants from the soil composition (Table 4).

In conclusion, it should be summarized that that heavy metal ions have different abilities to influence the content of nutrients and humus. At the same time, each heavy metal ion combines with some ion of another complex element and leads to a stressful state. It is possible to improve the agrochemical state of nutrients and humus from a stressful state only by reducing the ions of toxic elements in the soil or removing metal ions by phytoremediation.

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